

A New Synthesis of Isothioammelins and Isothioammelides Part I.

J. D. DHAKE

University Department of Chemistry & Laxminarayan Institute of Technology,
Nagpur University, Nagpur

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Interaction of carbon disulphide with 1*p* tolyl-3-amidino-S-benzylisothiocarbamide (V) has been shown to afford 2-thio-4-amino-6-*p*-tolylamino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (VI) and 1-*p*-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-mercaptobenzyl-1,3,5-isotriazine (VIII). VI in presence of alkali, rearranges into VII. VI, VII and VIII on reaction with benzylamine form the related *iso* thioammelins (IX). The reaction provides a new synthetic route to isotriazine derivatives.

The mercapto and amino derivatives of 1,3,5-triazines generally known as thioammelins and thioammelides can be prepared starting from cyanuric chloride¹. Some of these derivatives can also be obtained through the interaction of cyanoguanidine with ammonium thiocyanate², alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates³ and carbon disulphide⁴. The related isothioammelins and isothioammelides where the ring nitrogen(s) carry substituents do not, however, appear to have been reported and the above procedures do not offer much promise of their practical suitability for this purpose.

In an earlier communication from this laboratory⁵ it has been shown that 1-methyl-3-methylamidino-S-benzylisothiocarbamide (I) on reaction with carbon disulphide (route A) afforded 2,4-dimethylimino-6-thio-1,3,5-thiadiazine (II) which on treatment with dil. aq. alkali or repeated crystallisation underwent isomeric change into 1-methyl-4-methylimino-2,6-dithio-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (III). The other expected product (IV) of the alternative ring closure of the intermediate dithiocarbamic acid derivative along the route (B), however, could not be detected in the products. These changes can be stated as follows :

Bz = benzyl and Me = Methyl.

On investigating the reaction with 1-*p*-tolyl-3-amidino-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide, benzylmercaptan and hydrogen sulphide both were found to be eliminated and all the expected products *viz.*, the thiadiazine and the triazines corresponding to II, III and IV above were obtained.

The VIII was also obtained by the reaction of benzyl chloride with VI and VII. The VII and VIII both formed identical isothioammeline (IX) on reaction with benzylamine.

Thus the structures VI, VII and VIII assigned to the products are supported by the above reactions of benzyl chloride and benzylamine and also by their IR spectra (*vide* experimental part).

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *1-p-tolyl-3-amidino-S-benzylisothiocarbamide*: The required thiocarbamide was prepared by the interaction of *p*-tolylisothiocyanate and guanidine nitrate following the procedure of Kurzer⁶ but using molar quantity of sodium hydroxide instead of metallic sodium. On reaction with benzyl chloride in a refluxing ethanolic medium it afforded a crystalline hydrochloride identified as that of the related *S*-benzylisothiocarbamide; recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210°. Molar equivalent: found acidimetrically, 341; C₁₆H₁₈N₄S₂; HCl requires 334. On basification of the hydrochloride with aq. ammonia, the related free base was precipitated; crystals from ethanol, m.p. 90°. Found: S, 10.35; N, 18.48; C₁₆H₁₈N₄S₂ requires S, 10.77 and N, 18.79%.

2. *Interaction of Carbon disulphide with 1-p-tolyl-3-amidino-S-benzylisothiocarbamide*: When a solution of 1-*p*-tolyl-3-amidino-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide in benzene (1 g. in 50 ml.) was mixed with carbon disulphide (10 ml.) and heated on waterbath under a water cooled reflux condenser for 4 hrs, hydrogen sulphide and benzylmercaptan were found to be evolved and a pale yellow product separated (0.4 g.) on filtration and washed with acetone, m.p. 235°. When to the filtrate a fresh quantity of carbon disulphide (5 ml.) was added and heating resumed, after about 2 hrs, a second crop (0.2 g.) of the same product separated and was filtered out. The filtrate on evaporation left a syrupy mass which on addition of petroleum ether and vigorous stirring afforded a pale yellow solid (about 0.2 g.); on crystallisation from aq. ethanol m.p. 210°.

2-thio-4-imino-6-p-tolylamino-1,3,5-thiadiazine (VI) and 1-p-tolyl-2,6-dithio-4-imino-1,3,5-isotriazine (VII): The product of m.p. 235° on reaction with warm aq. sodium plumbite, was found easily desulphurisable. It was sparingly soluble in acetone, alcohol and chloroform and was insoluble in water. Found: S, 25.38; N, 22.12; C₁₀H₁₀N₄S₂ requires S, 25.61; N, 22.41%. This has been assigned structure VI (*vide infra*). The compound was soluble in ethanolic alkali but when such a solution was acidified, another pale yellow product, m.p. 260° (d), was precipitated.

This product (m.p. 260° d) is insoluble in ethanol, acetone and chloroform. It cannot be crystallised also from chlorobenzene or nitrobenzene. It was purified by reprecipitating it with acetic acid from its ethanolic alkaline solutions. Found: S, 25.49; N, 22.60; C₁₀H₁₀N₄S₂ requires S, 25.61; N, 22.41%. It has been assigned structure VII and appears to be formed by the isomeric change of the thiadiazine VI. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm⁻¹). 3400m, NH-stretching (Lit⁷, 3400–3100); 1640 s, C = N- (Lit^{8a}, 1685–1582); 1550 vs. 1,3,5-triazine (Lit^{8b}, 1550); 1280, 1220 w, -NH-C-, (Lit^{8c}, 1400–700);

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ | \\ \text{S} \end{array}$$
 1060 w, s-triazine (Lit⁷, 1065); 750 vs. "iso" form of triazine (Lit^{8d}, 795–750).

1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-mercaptobenzyl-1,3,5-isotriazine (VIII): The product with m.p. 210° is soluble in alcohol and acetone but insoluble in water. On heating it decomposed and a strong odour of benzylmercaptan was perceptible. On reaction with warm aq. sodium plumbite it gave yellow precipitate of lead mercaptide. It also liberated benzylmercaptan on dissolving in alcoholic alkali and acidification with hydrochloric acid. Found: S, 18.46; N, 16.24; C₁₇H₁₆N₄S₂ requires S, 18.82; N, 16.47%. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm⁻¹) and it has been assigned structure VIII. 3400 m, NH stretching, (Lit⁷, 3400–3100); 1600 m, C = N (Lit^{8a}, 1685–1582); 1560 s, 1,3,5-triazine (Lit^{8b}, 1550); 1425 m, S-CH₂ (Lit^{8e}, 1435–1410); 1210, HN-C- (Lit^{8c}, 1400–700); N-C-N (Lit^{8f}, 1200);

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{S} \\ | \\ \text{S} \end{array}$$
 785, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit^{8d}, 795–750).

3. *1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-benzylamino-1,3,5-isotriazine (IX)*. Reaction of benzylamine with VIII: When a mixture of VIII (0.5 g.) and benzylamine (2 ml.) was heated at 180° for one hour, smell of benzylmercaptan was perceptible and on cooling and addition of cold aq. hydrochloric acid to the product a soft solid was obtained; crystals from aq. ethanol, m.p. 135°. Found: S, 9.38; N, 21.41; C₁₇H₁₇N₅S requires S, 9.90; N, 21.67%. Its IR spectrum showed the following bands (cm⁻¹) and it has been assigned structure IX: 3400 s, NH stretching (Lit⁷, 3400–3100); 1625 w, C = N (Lit^{8a}, 1685–1582); 1550 vs. 1,3,5-triazine (Lit^{8b}, 1550); 1216 s, C = S (Lit^{8of}); 770 w, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit^{8d}, 795–750).

4. *1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-mercaptobenzyl-1,3,5-isotriazine (VIII)*: Interaction of benzyl chloride with VII. A mixture of VII (0.8 g.), ethanol (25 ml.) and benzylchloride (1 ml.) was heated under reflux until a clear solution was obtained. On concentrating to less than half of its original volume, cooling and adding ether a crystalline solid which was acidic to litmus was precipitated, m.p. 218°. On recrystallisation from ethanol, m.p. 220°. Molar equivalent: found acidimetrically 379.1, C₁₇H₁₆N₄S₂, HCl requires 376.5. On basification with ammonia, the related free base was obtained; crystals from aq. ethanol m.p. 210°.

Found : S, 18.56; N, 16.52; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires S, 18.82; N, 16.47%. It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with the product, m.p. 210°, obtained by the direct interaction of V and carbon disulphide.

The hydrochloride and the related free base m.p. 212° (Found : S, 18.30; N, 16.34; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2$ requires S, 18.82; N, 16.47%) obtained by the benzylation of VI were found identical through m.p. and m.m.p. with the hydrochloride of VIII and VIII itself respectively obtained by the benzylation of VII.

5. 1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-benzylamino-1,3,5-isotriazine (IX) : Interaction of benzylamine with VII. A mixture of VII (0.8 g.) and benzylamine (2 ml.) was heated at 180° for 1 hr when H_2S was found to be evolved. The resultant liquid on pouring in cold, dil. hydrochloric acid afforded a sticky solid; crystals from aq. ethanol, m.p. 135°. Found : S, 9.49; N, 21.29; $C_{17}H_{17}N_5S$ requires S, 9.90; N, 21.67%. It gave no depression in m.m.p. with the product obtained by the interaction of benzylamine with VIII.

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